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The Influence of Government Supported CPD of Engineers on the Development of Engineering Education: TPU case

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ABSTRACT

The article is focused on continuing professional development (CPD) of engineers and technical professionals in Russia supported by the Government and its influence on the development of engineering education. Specifically, it explores a case of Tomsk Polytechnic University (TPU) that took part in the Presidential programme for advanced training of engineering personnel (2012–2014) and in the Departmental special-purpose programme aimed at professional development of engineers and technicians (2015–2016). The study incorporates a mix of quantitative and qualitative methods that helped define the common features of engineering CPD programmes and provided insights into the contribution of such programmes to the development of engineering education and university-industry collaboration. In particular, according to the study results the delivery of government supported CPD programmes for engineers encouraged the engagement of industrial companies in development and delivery of bachelor's and master's degree engineering educational programmes. The TPU experience is a good example for development of university-industry strategic partnership that might result in a higher quality of engineering education.

Conference Key Areas: Continuing Engineering Education and Lifelong Learning, Engineering Skills, Sustainability and Engineering Education

Keywords: engineering education, continuing professional development, university-industry collaboration, engineering personnel

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INTRODUCTION

Continuing professional development (CPD) of engineers and technical professionals is an essential factor for the development of human capital which tends to have a great impact on industry evolution and economic growth. The ability to be engaged in independent lifelong learning and to undertake CPD activities sufficient to maintain and extend his or her competence is considered to be one of the key professional engineer's competences [1–5]. Traditionally, continuing engineering courses include in-house training and courses offered by educational institutions, private organizations or professional communities and associations (see e.g. Engineers Ireland, Engineers Australia). In Japan, continuing engineering education in enterprises and research organizations is widespread [6], whereas in other countries the universities continue to be the preferred CPD provider while they combine research, innovation and education [7, 8]. The involvement in engineering CPD is a challenging task for the universities and it requires an active interaction between the university and the company during development, delivery and evaluation of CPD courses [9]. The European bodies such as the European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI) and the European Federation of National Engineering Associations (FEANI) are working in the field of engineering CPD, they set CPD policy and guidelines as well as provide methodological support and launch some relevant projects and studies in the field.

The formation of highly qualified engineering personnel belongs to the strategic objectives of the Russian Government. In 2012, the Executive Order On the 2012–2014 Presidential programme for advanced training of engineering personnel was signed. The programme aimed at professional development of engineering personnel working in the strategic industries as well as at modernization of engineering education in the context of strategic partnership of Russian educational institutions and industrial companies. In 2015, it was decided to launch the similar Departmental special-purpose programme aimed at support and promotion of the best practices in engineering CPD.

1 DEPARTMENTAL SPECIAL-PURPOSE PROGRAMME “ADVANCED TRAINING OF ENGINEERING PERSONNEL IN THE YEARS 2015–2016”

1.1 Programme description

The Departmental special-purpose programme “Advanced training of engineering personnel in the years 2015-2016” was launched by the Order of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation in May 2015 [10]. The programme is aimed at support and promotion of the best CPD courses for engineers and technicians in the priority areas of science and technology in the Russian Federation including nanosystem industry, information and telecommunication systems, life sciences, sustainable use of natural resources, transport and space systems, energy efficiency, power saving, nuclear power engineering, etc. The programme goal is to increase the contribution of educational institutions to the development of human resources in strategic industry fields that might stipulate technological modernization of economy, increase in labour productivity, and creation of highly productive jobs.

The objectives of the programme include the development of public-private partnership by professional development of engineering personnel and modernization of content and educational technologies of engineering CPD courses. The training courses that take part in the programme must be developed by Russian

educational institutions in collaboration with targeted enterprises and industrial companies, which have to provide no less than 50% co-funding. Besides engineers, there are master's degree and post-graduate students, as well as engineering educators among the trainees.

The programme incorporates the concept of the Triple Helix of university-industry-government relationships proposed by Etzkowitz [11]. The universities develop and deliver engineering CPD courses in strong collaboration with industry companies to develop human resources of engineering enterprises and this process is supported by the government and industrial companies. All the participants of this process have got their benefits: the government gets highly qualified engineering personnel and economic growth as a consequence; the universities develop the relationships with industry followed by an active engagement of employers in their activities; the industry companies can reduce expenses on staff professional development by sending the employees to the government supported CPD courses chosen in competitive selection process.

1.2 Programme results

The competitive selection of CPD courses for engineering personnel organised by the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation allowed choosing 385 professional training courses for engineers and technicians offered by 82 educational institutions. Over 8000 engineers and technicians employed by 751 industrial companies took part in these courses. Under the terms of the programme no less than 20% of trainees (1804 persons) went on on-the-job training on the premises of Russian industrial companies and engineering centers, no less than 10% (979 persons) went on practical training on the premises of industrial companies and engineering centers abroad in 38 countries [10].

The feedback results gathered from CPD courses' graduates show that 96% of respondents point out, that the competencies developed during the training courses are highly relevant for their professional activity. About 90% of industrial companies recognize that this government supported programme has contributed a lot to improvement of the company effectiveness [12].

One of the important results of the Departmental special-purpose programme "Advanced training of engineering personnel in the years 2015-2016" is the creation of the engineering CPD courses' pool incorporating the best practices of vocational education and training courses (see <http://engineer-cadry.ru/>).

2 GOVERNMENT SUPPORTED CPD COURSES FOR ENGINEERS: TPU CASE

2.1 Course development and delivery

Tomsk Polytechnic University (TPU), one of the leading engineering universities in Russia took part in the Departmental special-purpose programme "Advanced training of engineering personnel in the years 2015-2016" as well as in the 2012–2014 Presidential programme for advanced training of engineering personnel. As a result of the competitive selection in the frameworks of these programmes TPU gained the right to deliver about 40 CPD courses. More than 700 engineers and technicians from 125 Russian industrial companies were trained (see *Table 1*).

Table 1. Results of the government supported programmes aimed at the advanced training of engineering personnel: TPU experience

Year	Number of programmes	Number of trainees	Number of companies
2012	4	117	23
2013	10	187	27
2014	9	135	25
2015	6	90	12
2016	12	197	38
Total	41	726	125

In 2016 TPU gained the right to deliver 12 CPD training courses for engineering personnel, it was the best result among the Russian universities that took part in the competitive selection. The high quality of TPU courses was recognized, their common features are described below.

- 1) **Targeted course design.** The collaboration between a university and a company is critical in the establishment of an effective framework for professional development [9]. The intended learning outcomes of each CPD course offered by TPU were developed based on stakeholder needs and requirements of correspondent professional standards. The outcome-based approach helped develop in-demand training courses, which graduates demonstrate professional and general (non-technical) competencies relevant for a particular industry field.
- 2) **Adoption of the best practices in engineering education.** Being the member of leading international organizations and initiatives dealing with engineering education including SEFI, IGIP, CDIO Initiative, etc., TPU adopts and implements modern teaching and learning approaches. The university has developed a coherent CPD system aimed at the development of faculty competencies [13]. The system combines over 40 training programmes that contribute to the development of key faculty competencies such as ability to design, deliver and evaluate educational programmes in compliance with national and international standards, ability to use various educational technologies and active learning methods, ability to conduct students' project and research work, etc. Besides, there is a list of programmes aimed at the development of specialized faculty competencies connected with design, implementation and operation of engineering products, systems and technologies.

The CPD courses for engineering personnel offered by TPU are delivered using collaborative learning, problem-based learning, project work, integrated learning experience, e-learning technologies (some courses are supported by e-courses in LMS Moodle). Each course consists of lectures and practical studies in university premises (more than 72 h), internship in Russian leading industry companies and engineering centers (to 50% of trainees), and internship abroad (to 30% of trainees). The trainees develop professional theoretical skills in addition to the practical work skills; they also gain the experience of working abroad in an international team which is very important in the process of internationalization of engineering profession.

- 3) **Facilities and equipment.** The CPD courses are provided with engineering workspaces, laboratories and modern equipment to emphasize hands-on

learning. TPU has a few authorised centers (Hughes-TPU Center, SolidWorks Authorised Training Center, Accreditation, Monitoring and Diagnostics Regional Center, etc.). The created learning environments allow developing practical engineering skills (see CDIO engineering workspaces [14]).

- 4) **Strategic partnership.** TPU has a well-developed network of contacts with Russian and foreign industrial companies, research and engineering centers. It helped find partner for development and delivery of CPD courses for engineering personnel to provide on-the-job training and internships in Russia and abroad.

2.2 Findings and interpretation

The results of a questionnaire delivered to the industrial companies which employees took part in the TPU professional training courses show their positive attitude towards these government supported CPD programmes. The main results are the following:

- 70% recognize the need for lifelong learning.
- 67% are ready to take part in TPU career events for students and graduates.
- 67% have a wish to be involved in students' job-placement.
- 56% want to make some research projects in cooperation with TPU.

All the respondents expressed a wish to be engaged in development, delivery of engineering educational programmes and assessment of learning outcomes. It is a crucial result in the context of quality assurance of engineering educational programmes, as according to the accreditation criteria of the Association for Engineering Education of Russia (AEER) used for educational programmes in engineering and technology, the employers as the main stakeholders have to take part in the definition of learning goals and intended learning outcomes, as well as in the evaluation of programme graduates [15].

The companies' representatives highlighted in their interviews that the government supported CPD courses helped save financial expenses for the professional development of their staff. They also pointed out a high quality of methodological support and qualification of faculty members engaged in training courses. They confirmed that the engineering CPD courses offered by TPU are in full correspondence with current industry needs.

These results demonstrate that delivery of government supported CDP courses for engineers and technicians has a positive impact on both industry companies and educational institutions as well as on the development of industry-university collaboration.

3 SUMMARY

The development of human capital is a crucial aspect for economic growth of any country. The government supported programmes for advanced training of engineers and technical professionals realized in Russia in 2012-2016 could be a good example of public-private partnership by professional development of engineering personnel. The case of Tomsk polytechnic university shows that these programmes have a positive influence on the development of engineering education. In particular, they contribute to the engagement of industry representatives in design and delivery of engineering educational programmes. The companies which employees took part in CPD courses offered by TPU expressed a strong wish to develop partnership with the university.

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